

Triphasic-aided Liver Lesion Segmentation in Non-contrast CT: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Triphasic-aided Liver Lesion Segmentation in Non-contrast CT

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

TriALS

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Liver lesion detection and characterization often rely on contrast agents to enhance the visibility of abnormalities due to the limited soft tissue resolution of non-contrast CT (NCCT) scans. However, global supply chain disruptions caused by COVID-19, combined with economic instability in developing countries, have significantly impacted the availability of contrast agents. In Egypt, liver cancer ranks as the most prevalent cancer, representing 20–35% of all cancer cases, according to the WHO Globocan Report (2020) and the Egyptian National Cancer Registry (2014). Given the high burden of liver cancer, national campaigns targeting hepatitis treatment have been initiated to mitigate its impact on the population.

At MICCAI 2024 in Africa, we established TriALS as a benchmark for liver lesion segmentation on NCCT scans. We demonstrated the potential of utilizing multi-phase data to enhance the training process, thereby improving lesion detection accuracy in NCCT imaging, particularly as a substitute for contrast-enhanced imaging in resource-limited settings. Not only TriALS can mitigate the contrast shortage problem, but it can also help reduce contrast-related complications and significantly lower imaging costs in an already economically affected population.

Despite our progress, the task remains highly challenging, underscoring the need for cross-regional collaboration and external validation. Building on TriALS 2024, we are extending TriALS to MICCAI 2025 in Asia by integrating a diverse, multi-center, multi-vendor dataset encompassing imaging from African (Egyptian) and Asian (Chinese) institutions, providing robust variability for cross-regional training and evaluation. Liver cancer remains a critical global health issue, particularly in Asia, where seven of the top 10 countries worldwide with the highest liver cancer mortality rates are located. Notably, China accounts for approximately 40% of liver cancer cases globally, with 367,657 cases out of the 866,136 reported worldwide, according to the World Cancer Research Fund (2022).

TriALS 2025's goal is twofold: (1) to advance liver lesion segmentation in regions with limited access to contrast imaging, such as Africa, and (2) to achieve detection accuracy comparable to contrast-enhanced imaging in well-resourced areas like China. Through this effort, TriALS aims to deliver high liver lesion detection accuracy, offering a sustainable and globally relevant solution for liver cancer detection.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Automated Liver Lesion Segmentation, Non-Contrast CT, Multi-Phase Contrast-Enhanced Imaging, Multi-Center Multi-Vendor Dataset, AI for Resource-Limited Settings, Interactive Segmentation

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

TriALS 2025 builds on the success of its 2024 edition by expanding its scope to Asia, introducing two key novelties: (1) A multi-center, multi-vendor dataset from African (Egyptian) and Asian (Chinese) institutions, making it the first challenge to address liver lesion segmentation with such extensive cross-regional variability; (2) Task-wise, it focuses on the critical challenge of lesion detection in resource-limited settings using non-contrast CT (NCCT) imaging, while also aiming for accuracy comparable to contrast-enhanced imaging, thereby reducing imaging costs even in well-resourced settings.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Comprehensive Presentation of Results: TriALS incorporates a multi-phase, multi-center, and multi-vendor dataset, significantly increasing the complexity and depth of the results. A shorter timeframe may hinder a thorough exploration of these elements.

Audience Size and Interest: The substantial audience engagement during TriALS 2024 underscores strong community interest. Notably, the TriALS 2024 challenge day attracted around 30 on-site participants, exceeding the room's 25-seat capacity (several attendees had to stand or eventually left due to space). This interest extends beyond liver lesion segmentation to its broader potential for application in other organs, where AI might enhance or even obviate the need for contrast imaging. A longer session would facilitate deeper audience interaction, enabling in-depth discussions, valuable insights, and networking opportunities.

TriALS Evaluation Tracks: TriALS 2025 features two evaluation tracks: (1) a fully automated segmentation track using only NCCT images (with multi-phase data available for training), and (2) an interactive segmentation track with user-simulated clicks. Both tracks focus on the same underlying task of liver lesion segmentation, yet they require distinct methods and presentations.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We conservatively estimate approximately 30 participating teams for this year's TriALS challenge. In comparison, last year's challenge saw 35 teams request access to the dataset with signed consent, resulting in 24 submissions across both tasks. Of these, 7 international teams provided valid submissions and were ranked on the test set. Notably, the TriALS 2024 challenge day attracted around 30 on-site participants, exceeding the room's 25-seat capacity (several attendees had to stand or eventually left due to space).

Despite the late release, last year's training and evaluation code gained significant visibility and attention on GitHub: <https://github.com/xmed-lab/TriALS>. This year, we are building on the same successful framework, now incorporating a multi-center, multi-vendor dataset. Based on our experience and community feedback, we anticipate smoother access to both code and data, ensuring no delays that could hinder participating teams from submitting their algorithms.

By comparison, previous challenges like the Liver Tumor Segmentation Benchmark (LiTS) (doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2022.102680) featured 43 teams—17 participating in ISBI 2017 and 26 in MICCAI 2017. Similarly, challenges leveraging contrast-enhanced MRI data (atlas-challenge.u-bourgogne.fr/leaderboard) received over 10 submissions at MICCAI 2024.

Unlike single-phase CT datasets such as LiTS, which provide only PV-phase CT images, TriALS is distinguished by its use of multi-phase CT imaging. Our dataset includes non-contrast-enhanced (NC), arterial (ART), portal venous (PV), and delayed-phase CT images, aiming to raise the upper bound for liver lesion segmentation. To the best of our knowledge, TriALS is the first challenge to focus on lesion segmentation using multi-phase CT imaging, addressing a significant gap in the literature. Additionally, TriALS 2025 introduces a multi-center, multi-vendor dataset for multi-phase CT imaging, further enhancing the robustness and generalizability of the challenge.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Each team will be permitted to nominate up to two authors for a joint publication summarizing the challenge outcomes. The top-performing method from TriALS 2024 will serve as the baseline for all participants. Both the code and evaluation metrics are publicly available, and only teams whose methods outperform this baseline will be included in the joint publication.

A select number of teams, chosen based on the diversity and novelty of their solutions, will be invited to deliver oral presentations. To ensure the integrity of the joint publication, participants are required to refrain from independently publishing any related results until the joint challenge paper is published. An embargo period of 12 months, starting from the challenge date in September 2025 will apply. The data paper from last year's TriALS challenge is finalized, and the submission for the dataset and the challenge summary is expected to be available by March 2025.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Building on the success of TriALS 2024, we will continue using Synapse.org as the platform to manage and run the challenge effectively.

For the on-site component, we request a projector and screen to facilitate presentations and live demonstrations, along with loudspeakers and microphones to ensure clear and effective communication during discussions and presentations.

TASK 1: Triphasic-aided Liver Lesion Segmentation in Non-contrast CT

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

TriALS 2025 focuses on automated liver lesion segmentation in multi-phase CT, with an emphasis on non-contrast CT inference for resource-limited settings where contrast agents are unavailable. Given the challenging task of automated lesion segmentation, TriALS 2025 introduces an interactive track using click-based segmentation, enabling precise, user-guided lesion instance segmentation. This track aligns closely with real-world clinical workflows, allowing clinicians to highlight areas of suspicion and track lesions over time. Participants can then explore the potential of foundation model approaches leveraging prompts to enhance segmentation accuracy.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Automated Liver Lesion Segmentation, Non-Contrast CT, Multi-Phase Contrast-Enhanced Imaging, Multi-Center Multi-Vendor Dataset, AI for Resource-Limited Settings, Interactive Segmentation.

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Technical Team:

[The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong SAR]

Marawan Elbatel, Yi Qin, Xuanqi Huang, Haonan Wang, and Xiaomeng Li

[Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany]

Zdravko Marinov, Rainer Stiefelhagen

Clinical Team in Asia:

[Department of Radiology, Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Malignant Tumor Epigenetics and Gene Regulation, Sun Yat-Sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-Sen University, Guangzhou, China]

Wenhui Deng, Baoxun Li, Jiaji Mao, Huijun Hu, Jun Shen

Clinical Team in Africa:

[1*AI Center of Excellence, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt]

[2*Department of Radiology, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt]

Mohamed Ghonim 1*2*, Ahmed Abouelhoda 2*, Mohanad Ghonim 1*2*, Amr Muhammad Abdo Salem 1*2*, Nouran Elghitany 1*2*, Noha Elghitany 1*2*, Amira Adel 2*, Susan Adil Ali 2*, Aya Yassin 1*2*

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Marawan Elbatel (mkfmeibatel@connect.ust.hk)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Building on the success of TriALS 2024, we will continue using Synapse.org as the platform to manage and run the challenge effectively. Given the task's high complexity, each algorithm will be allowed up to 30 minutes per case for inference during testing. This ensures even advanced, resource-intensive methods can run to completion.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn53285416>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic, Semi automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed, and publicly available pre-trained models. Participants are allowed to use public data only if they are publicly available at the opening, when the challenge starts, including pre-trained models. Institutions can utilize private data to benchmark their algorithm, submission utilizing private data would not be eligible for awards.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The award policy represents the collaborative efforts of sponsors from Africa and Asia. Currently, the challenge is endorsed by SIG-AFRICAI, a Special Interest Group supported by the MICCAI society, and we will host the challenge awards under its auspices. Following last year's award policy, we also plan to seek sponsorship from the

Hong Kong University of Science and Technology.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be announced publicly and posted on the website.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each team will be permitted to nominate up to two authors for a joint publication summarizing the challenge outcomes. The top-performing method from TriALS 2024 will serve as the baseline for all participants. Both the code and evaluation metrics are publicly available, and only teams whose methods outperform this baseline will be included in the joint publication.

A select number of teams, chosen based on the diversity and novelty of their solutions, will be invited to deliver oral presentations. To ensure the integrity of the joint publication, participants are required to refrain from independently publishing any related results until the joint challenge paper is published. An embargo period of 12 months, starting from the challenge date in September 2025 will apply.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Building on the success of last year's challenge, participants are provided with a sample Docker submission featuring a baseline method, along with comprehensive step-by-step submission instructions. Additionally, the code for evaluation and metrics is made available to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Teams will submit their Docker containers via Synapse, and at the final testing stage, a detailed report on the methodology will be required.

Code repository: <https://github.com/xmed-lab/TriALS>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to submit three submissions for evaluating their algorithms on a validation sample to ensure the correctness of the docker container as well as provide preliminary results. For the final evaluation of

the test dataset, only the last submitted container will be used.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website and challenge registration opens: 1st April 2025

Training data release: 14th April 2025

Team registration open: 14th April 2025

Validation Phase Open: 5th May 2025

Team registration closes: on 1st September 2025

Docker submission deadline: 8th September 2025

Methodology submission: 15th September 2025

Challenge Day: (23rd or 27th of September 2025)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We acquired the Egyptian dataset, comprising 380 volumes, from Ain Shams University Hospitals in Egypt, with ethical approval obtained from the local Research Ethics Committee (FWA 000017585). Additionally, we obtained the Chinese dataset, consisting of 160 volumes, from the First Western Hospital in China, Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, also called the Second Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University (SYSU). We have obtained ethics approval from the relevant institutional review board for the Chinese dataset (approval number SYSKY202232701). All volumes were fully anonymized, with no personal identifiers, rendering them completely untraceable to ensure patient confidentiality.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation script is provided alongside a Docker baseline with detailed instructions for participants. The click simulation scripts will also be available to all participants so that they can replicate the click simulation on additional data, e.g., for fine-tuning.

This year, metrics will be separately reported for the African and Asian datasets.

Code Link: https://github.com/xmed-lab/TriALS/tree/main/eval_scripts

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are not required yet are encouraged to release their code as open-access.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

No conflict of interest. TriALS challenge is supported through independent funding with no direct sponsorship from commercial entities, ensuring impartiality in its execution. We will update MICCAI if a commercial sponsor is to be included.

Only the core organizing team will have access to test case labels, and this access will occur exclusively after the submission deadline to ensure unbiased evaluation. No participant or external entity will have access to the test case labels at any point before the challenge concludes.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning

- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening,Diagnosis,CAD,Decision support,Intervention planning,Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort includes future patients admitted to Ain Shams University Hospitals in Cairo, Egypt, and Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University in Guangzhou, China, who have undergone non-contrast abdominal CT and triphasic CT with detected liver lesions.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

A retrospective cohort of adult male and female patients aged over 18 years who underwent contrast-enhanced and non-contrast abdominal CT scans. The scans were obtained from the Radiology Departments at Ain Shams University Hospitals in Cairo, Egypt, and Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University in Guangzhou, China, with all four imaging phases, including non-contrast, available. Notably, in the former setting in AFRICA (Egypt), acquiring contrast-enhanced CT scans posed a challenge due to contrast shortage, while in the latter in Asia (China), contrast-enhanced scans were readily available; however, obtaining the paired non-contrast CT versions was a significant challenge due to clinical protocols and resource optimization in high-volume hospitals.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT without contrast and with contrast in different phases:

Time at which the acquisition is performed after iodinated contrast* agent injection:

- Arterial time: Upon bolus tracking in descending aorta by smart prep (usually about 35-45 sec post-injection);
- Portovenous time: 20 seconds post arterial (usually about 65 to 70 sec post-injection);
- Delayed time: 3 minutes post portovenous (Usually up to five minutes post-injection).

*Contrast agents used are variable due to changes in supply chains and limited import. Sometimes, non-ionic contrast agents ("Omnipaque") is used, when unavailable, ionic contrast agents ("Telebrix") is used.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For the fully automated segmentation tasks, no additional imaging data will be provided. However, for the interactive track, clicks will be supplied as a set of 3D coordinates corresponding to the image resolution. These clicks are pre-simulated based on expert-delineated ground truth masks, rather than generated by human raters during the challenge. This automated simulation (following established interactive segmentation methods) ensures that all participants receive identical, expert-like inputs for a fair comparison.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We collected the following information about patients when available: Age, Sex, Indication for scan, lesion (provisional) diagnosis based on the report, and Approximate lesion count. All data were kept in an anonymized format with reverse mapping only with the clinical lead in each participating hospital.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Liver visible as a whole in contrast and non-contrast enhanced CTs of the abdomen and pelvi-abdomen.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating

theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm is designed to automatically segment liver lesions, both without user interaction and with pre-simulated clicks provided as user inputs (Interactive Track).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Sensitivity, Precision, Accuracy, Applicability, Robustness, Interaction, Integration in workflow

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

- SIEMENS SOMATOM Force
- SIEMENS SOMATOM Sensation 64
- United Imaging uCT780
- GE Discovery CT750 HD
- GE Revolution EVO
- GE Healthcare Optima
- Toshiba Prime Aquilion
- GE BrightSpeed CT

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Data acquisition includes CT in different phases (without contrast, arterial, portal venous, delayed). Acquisition parameters vary in a normal range, and the time of the acquisition after the contrast agent (arterial, portal, delay) varies due to the vascularity diversity of patients.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Images were acquired across regions in Africa and Asia:

- 1) Ain Shams University Hospitals, Cairo, Egypt.
- 2) Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Radiology residents, specialists, and consultants with over 3, 5, and 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Following TriALS 2024, each case in the training set includes four 3D CT images (non-contrast, arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases) along with five sets of labels: individual labels for each phase (non-contrast, arterial, portal venous, and delayed) and combined labels registered to the non-contrast phase. All liver lesions are comprehensively annotated across these datasets. Additionally, for the interactive track, each training case contains a set of simulated click coordinates covering multiple liver lesions in the image.

For testing, validation will be performed in two separate scenarios: one using only the non-contrast CT images and the other using only the portal venous phase CT images, where liver lesions are most visibly represented. Additionally, for the interactive track, each testing and validation case contains a set of simulated click coordinates covering multiple liver lesions in the image.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Total: 80 cases for training (320 volumes), 10 for validation (40 volumes), and 50 for testing (200 volumes).

Divided as follows:

- Ain Shams University Hospitals, Cairo, Egypt: 60 cases for training (240 volumes), 10 for validation (40 volumes), and 30 for testing (120 volumes).
- Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Guangzhou, China: 20 cases for training (80 volumes) and 20 for testing (80 volumes).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

With the lack of publicly available multi-phase liver datasets—let alone multi-center, multi-vendor datasets—TriALS addresses this gap by providing a comprehensive dataset, with approximately 30% reserved as held-out testing to ensure robust result assessment. The lower number of cases from China compared to Egypt is due to challenges in obtaining paired non-contrast CT scans, as contrast-enhanced imaging is more readily available in China compared to Egypt.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

There is a strong imbalance between the semantic classes: lesion(s), and background.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The dataset for TriALS 2025 consists of 140 cases (560 volumes), combining previously seen data from TriALS 2024 with new, unpublished data:

Seen Data: 60 cases (240 volumes) from Ain Shams University Hospitals, Cairo, Egypt, were part of the TriALS 2024 training data and are pending publication.

Unseen Data: 80 cases (320 volumes), including 40 cases from Ain Shams University Hospitals and 40 cases from Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, are newly acquired and unpublished. We carefully curated the test set by excluding any cases with significant inter-phase misalignment or registration errors. This way, all test cases are of high quality and challenge the algorithms' capabilities without unfairly introducing annotation errors.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

We used a hybrid Human-Algorithm labeling scheme. Firstly, we deployed our algorithm for the preliminary segmentation of all scans by ensuring that the phases were well registered with non-rigid registration. We propagated the lesion from the most visible phase and added to it in other phases. Our algorithm has been trained on publicly available liver tumor datasets (LiTS) and a few-shot in-house data manually delineated by a medical doctor resident. Secondly, all segmentations in all phases are corrected when necessary and modified by a medical doctor resident. A team of 10 annotators performed the segmentations. Most volumes were reviewed by another medical doctor resident for inter-rater-variability. Finally, all cases were reviewed by a resident to ensure no mistakenly annotated pixels were found based on segment statistics. We aim to refine the segmentations for our second version and ensure that all volumes were reviewed by 2 annotators.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Lesion(s) segmentation: Lesions spanning 2 or more slices were included (around 3 mm in maximum diameter considering slice thickness of 1.25 mm in most volumes). We defined the characteristics of lesion to be considered for inclusion and our consultant radiologists set an exclusion criteria. We used 3D slicer for segmentation after training all annotators on it using recorded videos explaining the process and common encounters. We also had several troubleshooting sessions. Whenever we faced a hard decision (unagreeable by all) we referred to our consultants for resolving the issues. Our inclusion/exclusion criteria included:

- Inclusion

- o Age > 18 years.
- o Contrast-enhanced abdominal CT with 4 phases available for each patient.
- o Liver lesion mentioned in the report.

- Exclusion

- o Artifacts significantly affecting image quality on visual assessment.
- o Total main portal vein thrombosis.
- o Advanced cases of cirrhosis by CT assessment.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

A team of 10 medical annotators performed the segmentations. Least experienced had 1 year of radiology experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

- Training Cases:

For the training set, annotations from all CT phases (non-contrast, arterial, portal venous, and delayed) were combined and registered to the non-contrast phase. The process involved the following steps:

- 1) Rigid Registration: Annotations from arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases were aligned with the non-contrast CT phase using rigid registration to correct for positional offsets.
- 2) Non-Rigid Registration: To address phase-specific deformations, non-rigid transformations were applied to achieve finer alignment.
- 3) Label Fusion for Combined Labels: The merged labels were generated using majority voting of all lesions annotated across the phases, ensuring comprehensive coverage of all lesions that are unseen by doctors in some phases (i.e non-contrast).
- 4) Quality Assurance: The resulting combined labels were reviewed by radiologists to verify that they accurately represented all lesions across phases, particularly those unseen in certain modalities.

- Validation and testing Cases:

- a) Phase-Specific Evaluation: Each phase (non-contrast and portal venous) was evaluated separately using the corresponding phase-specific annotation.
- b) Combined Labels Evaluation (Non-Contrast): For non-contrast CT images, the combined labels (created by merging annotations from all phases during training) were evaluated to specifically assess the AI's ability to detect lesions that may be missed by doctors in non-contrast CT but are visible in other modalities.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images are in their native CT modality space, mirroring the 'raw' format commonly encountered in clinical settings. We challenge participants to tackle data pre-processing in novel and creative ways (e.g. normalization, windowing). While our baseline code release will encompass a data preprocessing scheme, we encourage participants to explore and apply their unique methods.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

There exist uncertainties in the image annotations. For that purpose, we use a hybrid Human-Algorithm labeling scheme and provide inter-reader variability, with cases reviewed by at least two medical residents, if no consensus between them, the scan is reviewed by additional radiologists (more than three years of experience). In all cases, non-contrast CT scans are acquired with variable slice thicknesses of 1.25/5/10 mm (according to the CT it is performed on usually) compared to contrast-enhanced CT where the slice thickness is usually 1.25/5 mm. Another issue that was faced was the trial to actually find some lesions in the non-contrast phase and therefore annotate them. This might not be always avoidable and we might accept not being able to annotate some lesions in the non-contrast phase alone.

When faced with such an issue of having a lesion on contrast-enhanced phases yet not being able to locate them on non-contrast images, we resort to non-rigid registration and label propagation from the phase where the lesion is most visible. In case we are faced with any artifacts, we resort to experienced radiologists to check for the possibility of excluding such studies.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

No other source of error.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We follow established challenges, LiTS (doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2022.102680) and ATLAS (<https://atlas-challenge.u-bourgogne.fr/>) to compute the metrics for our challenge, focusing on per-case voxel-wise segmentation metrics:

- Dice Similarity Coefficient.
- Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASD).
- 5 mm Surface Dice (SD).
- Maximum Symmetric Surface Distance (MSD):

Acknowledging the distinctive nature of our challenge, which involves the segmentation of lesions in a multi-phase setting, we will adapt the application of these metrics in two distinct scenarios:

- 1) In the presence of multi-phase imaging data during inference.
- 2) In scenarios relying solely on non-contrast CT data, without access to multi-phase imaging.

To evaluate algorithm performance in the interactive track, models will be tested across 10 iterative click steps (one tumor and one background click per step). At each step, segmentation quality will be assessed using the four

evaluation metrics DSC, ASD, SD, and MSD. For each of the four metrics, we will compute the area under the curve that represents the relationship between the number of click iterations (x-axis, spanning from 0 to 10) and the corresponding metric values (y-axis) by using the trapezoidal rule to approximate the area. In addition, we will compute the final value of each metric after all clicks have been applied. This will result in a comprehensive set of 8 interactive metrics per image, capturing both the cumulative performance across an increasing number of interactions and the final performance after all interactions.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics, emphasizing clinical relevance, aim to enhance liver lesion(s) segmentation by leveraging multi-phase data.

Addressing the shortage of contrast in our target cohort for the final biomedical application, we prioritize algorithms advancing tumor detection even without contrast-enhanced phases.

For the interactive track, the area under the click-to-metric curves estimates how effectively a model leverages user-provided clicks over 10 iterative steps to refine segmentation. Responsiveness to user interactions is a critical factor in interactive segmentation workflows. A larger area for DSC and SD curves, combined with a smaller area for ASD and MSD curves, signifies the model's ability to efficiently translate minimal user input into accurate, clinically relevant segmentations. This capability is particularly beneficial for interactive annotation workflows, as it minimizes the time and effort required to delineate complex liver lesions, enhancing both efficiency and practicality for clinicians working with portal venous phase CT imaging. The performance after the last click represents the segmentation quality after processing the full set of 10 tumor and 10 background clicks. This reflects the algorithm's ability to deliver high-quality results within a fixed interaction budget.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Rank then aggregate. Specifically, we follow the following steps:

- 1) Individual Metric Ranking: We compare the performance of the algorithms on each metric for all teams individually.
- 2) Aggregated Ranking for Final Evaluation: The mean rank of each algorithm is computed across all metrics providing the final rank for the leaderboard.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We assign the worst score on all metrics for missing predictions. Specifically, a missing segmentation will receive 0 for overlap-based metrics (Dice, Jaccard), 1.0 for error-based metrics like VOE (indicating maximum error), and very large penalty values for surface-distance metrics (e.g., ASSD, RMSD, MSD) and volume difference. In practice, we cap these at a high constant to represent worst-case performance, consistent with LiTS challenge standards (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2022.102680>).

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The 'rank then aggregate' approach is utilized to favor algorithms that perform consistently well across all metrics. Notably, when evaluating diverse metrics that may not lend themselves to direct normalization or comparison, 'rank then aggregate' promotes fairness and transparency.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test will be employed following confirmation of non-normal distribution through the Shapiro-Wilk test.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Being robust against outliers and non-normal data, we selected the Wilcoxon signed rank due to its lack of reliance on the assumption of normal distribution.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A